

Integrating Social Media in Classroom: A Case Study of High Intermediate 3 & 4 at LBPP LIA Depok

Abstract

At LBPP LIA, the last level in English for Adult program is High Intermediate (HI) 4 and for a long time this level has given many difficulties to its class teacher and students alike. The difficulties of this level stem from the fact that it is the last level in EA program which students have to complete before they can complete English for Adults program at LBPP LIA. To pass HI 4, students have to pass its final test which consists of Written Test (WT), a combination of multiple choice exam and essay writing, and Oral Test (OT), a PowerPoint presentation. Teaching students and covering the lessons in student book are not big problems but the big challenges are guiding students in Essay writing and preparing them for their Final Test. All these are multiplied with the fact that HI 4 teacher and her/his students can only meet twice a week with a duration of 105 minutes/one session and they need to achieve positive result in just two and a half months. This is simply not enough for the class teacher to finish text book materials, to prepare students for their final test and to guide them in writing their essays, which will be the material for OT. Fortunately, an alternative approach present itself in the form of email and social media (Soc-Med) on internet. A HI 4 teacher used emails and soc-meds (Facebook and Posterous) extensively as mediums of engaging his students in their learning, preparation for final test and doing essay consultation. The efforts of using internet as the bridge to cross the time and space between the teacher and his students successfully produced an encouragingly positive result.

Keywords: Facebook, Posterous, Classblog, Social Media, Blended Learning.

I. Background

LBPP LIA offers various English programs and one of them is English for Adults (EA), which is divided into 3 levels and each level is divided into 4 sub-levels. The last levels in EA program are HI 3 and 4 which are particularly very challenging because they demand time, energy, and efforts from both the teacher and students sides to achieve the ultimate goal of completing EA program. Since a lot of hopes and expectations are placed on these levels, they become great burdens on both of the class teacher and students.

The lesson materials in HI 3 and 4 are topic based, ranging from China's economic expansion to Educational problems in US. With lesson's contents as equal as university level, teaching them to students who are mostly at High School level can be convoluted. Since each lesson emphasizes the Reading, Writing, and analytical skill (less on Listening and Speaking skill), the output products take the form of essay writing, mini presentation, or group discussion/mini debate. With five lessons in HI-3 and three lessons in HI-4, the problems in a class teacher's hands are how to teach the lessons to students, prepare students to pass the final test in each level, especially at HI-4, and to prepare their final assignment of HI 4.

To pass HI-3, students have to take Promotion Test which is based on the lessons in Student Book. The test consists of two types: Written (WT) and Oral Test (OT). The WT takes form in Multiple Choice (MC) type (60 items=60 points) and Essay Writing (EW) (40 points). As to HI-4, the test materials come from student book but its difficulty increases with small difference it the format of Final Test. Though the test format of HI-4 is similar to HI-3, its OT has a little twist because it is in the form of PowerPoint presentation, replacing the interview model of HI-3. The presentations are based on essays, written by students under direct supervision of class teacher. So, HI-4's teacher must supervise students' essays and she/he have to regularly meet students for essay consultation. To make matter more complex, the scoring of WT weighs more on EW than MC. This means that the Writing section HI-4 Final Test will play a dominant role in deciding students' final

score. If students score in Essay Writing is low, they cannot pass HI-4, especially if the MC section is also low.

These matters of teaching HI-3 and 4 are further compounded with limited time for face-to-face interaction, since the class teacher and students meet only twice a week (every Monday and Wednesday and for only 105 minutes per session). Obviously, it is hard to expect the class teacher and his students to be able to get optimal result, for they have few opportunities to interact outside class schedule. On one side, students are too busy with school activities, so they have little time to consult their class teacher at English Course. On the other side, the class teacher is only around during his teaching schedule. As a result, HI-3 and 4 carry constant difficulties to both class teacher and students and the problems are formulated as follow:

- Covering all lessons in HI 3 and 4 textbook right on schedule.
- Preparing students for the final test of HI 3 and 4 (written and oral).
- Guiding and supervising essay writing (in HI 4).
- Preparing students presentation (oral test of HI 4).

Luckily, 2 social medias and 3 computer softwares overcame the problems in the hands of the class teacher and his HI-3 and 4's students.

Procedure

There have been numerous researches done on using internet to support teaching learning activities in EFL and those researches have yielded dramatic improvement in teacher-students interaction and brought out positive learning progress. However, most of the researches focused on using blogs (Jati and Herini, 2006; Soares, 2008) and soc-net for teaching a specific skill of language, such as, writing, speaking, or reading (Kho and Chuah, 2012; Bhattachary and Chauhan, 2010; Millington and Smith, 2012; Wu and Hsu). On the other side, there are a few researches about integrating blog and soc-net to support students learning outside classroom or to extend teacher-students interaction. One notable effort to optimize internet power for extra teaching learning interactions has been pioneered by Salman Khan who creates videocasts on teaching Maths and shares them in his YouTube channel; Khan Academy (Khan, 2011). Now the channel has garnered millions of views and gained praises from educational world (Noer 2012), even drawing support from Bill Gates (Thompson 2011). Khan's success inspired the researcher to try out similar thing with a HI 3 and 4 class and to prove if integrating classroom activities with blogs and soc-net could really improve students' performance and enhance teacher-student interaction.

On paper, blending socnet/socmed with classroom activities benefits both students and teacher. For instance, it allows peer collaboration among students. A student who has a problem with a lesson may post her/his question in class blog and expects a classmate to give answer. Another way, students may share opinions about what they have learned and her/his friends will reply with their own opinions. This way, students will have a wonderful discussion which can improve their comprehension of classroom's subject. Class teacher can also start a discussion in FB group by asking a question which any student can answer. If a teacher provides students with videocasts or audio podcasts, he helps them to be independent learners outside classroom who can manage the pace of their own learning (Pinkman 2005). Furthermore, the benefit of videocasts/podcasts is to allow students to review their lessons anytime they want (Ronchetti 2009). The videocasts/podcasts will stimulate students further if they are authentic, made by teacher him/herself, making them attractive to students' needs.

To extend teacher student interaction beyond classroom, the teacher would optimize two soc-med websites as mediums for sharing teaching medias and engaging students outside classroom. For this purpose, the teacher selected FB and Posterous (recently defunct) to support his

plan. FB was chosen because it was, and is, the most popular soc-net which the teacher and his students were active in. With FB group and its message channel, the teacher would share doc. files, videos, news or notifications, and give essay consultation with students. On students' side, FB would be a channel to ask questions regarding their study. Although FB facilitates multi media sharing, it has limited capacity (max. 20 MB). As a result, the teacher used Posterous blog which supported larger media sharing, up to 100 MB,: videos, audio files, docs and photos. Moreover, Posterous accepted embedded link from another website. For instance, the class teacher could create an online quiz on a website which could be embedded to class blog at Posterous. This allowed students to do online quiz right on class blog and got the result instantly.

Classblog and FB Group would be meaningless if the content is not contextual with students's activities in class. Therefore, the teacher utilized three great computer softwares--Keynote, Audacity, MPEG Sreamclip--to create blog's content in the form of audio/video podcasts. The podcasts would be about the lessons in HI-3 and materials for the preparation of HI-4's final test. The teacher used Keynote (a presentation software) to create teaching slideshows which were exported into video podcasts and were enhanced using MPEG Streamclip. In addition, the teacher made audio podcasts (MP3) using Audacity (an open source audio editing software). Audacity was also used to modify audio files for TOEFL preparation test. Then, the teacher's uploaded his audio/video podcasts into a blog, so his students could watch the videos online or download them for offline usage. Students could use the videocasts to review their lessons outside classroom, thus creating a continuous learning process. Besides, podcasts would benefit absent students to catch up with lessons progress, thereby minimizing the gap of progress among students in a classroom.

First Experiment

The integration of email and soc-med in HI-3 class began for the first time on Term 4/2011(October-December) and continued in HI-4 throughout Term 1/2012 (January-March). The class was HI 3 and the schedule was Monday-Wednesday (17:00-16:45). There were 17 students in the classroom and, right from the beginning, the teacher invited them to join HI 3 & 4 FB group and class blog (both closed groups). Students participation did not go easily because a few students did not have FB account and some students had difficulty with opening an account at Posterous. With a careful approach and assistance, the students could successfully go through the process of opening accounts in FB and Posterous.

The process of teaching learning interactions in classroom was the same with any regular classroom. Teacher covered a lesson by giving explanation, having discussion with students, giving assignments, and grading students' works. Outside his classroom, the teacher engaged his students using a classblog and FB group. Usually, he posted casual greeting, sharing motivational words, or notifications of class activities. Since FB could not accept large files, the teacher uploaded large files-videos, audios-to classblog and shared its link in FB group. In addition, he filled the blog with class schedule and docs (Words and PPTs), focusing on grammar material and lesson content of HI 3 book. The routine was, every time the teacher finished a lesson, he created a slideshow using Keynote and shared the file in class blog. Not only that, the teacher also created online quizzes (using ProProf Quiz service) for extra grammar exercise. The quizzes, focusing on Grammar points in HI-3 Student Book, were created using ProProfQuiz.com and it was embedded to classroom blog, enabling students to do the exercise right inside the class blog and got result directly. In an effort to prepare students for HI 3 final test, the teacher uploaded TOEFL-like exercises (PDF files) into class blog which students could download and did on their own time. Since the teacher realized that his students always had difficulty with Listening part in HI's final test, he also shared audio materials for TOEFL test via classblog. After uploading the files, the teacher gave students four days to do the exercise before he shared the answer key through FB group. If students had had confusion about the test, they were allowed to ask questions in classroom or via internet. Besides

sharing answer key of TOEFL prep. test, the teacher used FB group as a way of communicating with his students.

At HI-4 (Term 1/2012), teacher resumed the soc-med classroom integration with a shift in focus. From the beginning, the teacher directed FB group for essay consultation, because HI-4 students had started writing their essays. In practice, students wrote their essay draft starting from the first paragraph and submit it via FB or email. This way, teacher could read students' drafts before class and made comments about it. Furthermore, email and FB also facilitated essay consultation outside class hour. Since the class schedule was on Monday and Wednesday, students could only met their teacher twice a week, and there would be four days gap before the next session on Monday. To overcome the gap, students had essay drafts consultation by email/FB message. For instance, students sent their drafts on Friday. Teacher read the drafts on Saturday, gave his comments, and sent them back on Saturday night. Students received the drafts instantaneously, made necessary revision, and brought the revised drafts on Monday. In classroom, teacher and students discussed the drafts and teacher would ask students to revise their drafts and submit it again via emails. Using this technic, students double timed their essay writing and made quick progress. In fact, some diligent students even consulted their drafts four times a week.

Another shift with soc-meds usage was not making slideshows about lesson materials because HI-4 student book only contained three lessons and they were fairly easy to be covered with teacher's explanation, students' group work, and paper assignment. Also, there was no online quiz because the teacher assumed that students would not have time to do it due to writing essays task and experience in HI-3 showed that less than 10 students did that test. For replacement, the teacher opted to upload PDFs of TOEFL preparation materials to class blog because HI 4's final test resembles TOEFL exam. Besides, the TOEFL test has listening section that could help preparing students for listening part of HI 4's final exam. As experienced by the class teacher with his past classes, HI-4 students often got low score in WT due to their inability to get >35 correct items in MC. This put the students' fate hanging on a thread, especially if their essay scores are also low. The source of the problem was >10 mistakes made by his previous students in Listening section (20 items). Therefore, giving this class a TOEFL test (complete with audio files for Listening part) would improve the current students' skill in doing listening part.

Nearing the end of term, when students had finished their essays and about to begin presentation preparation, the teacher used FB group and class blog to do presentation consultation. Students sent their proposed slideshow (PPT) via FB group/message and teacher would review them before he gave his agreement. To give guidance, teacher shared guidance to proper presentation by uploading PPT and Word files to classblog. Moreover, the classblog featured video records of students' presentation practice in classroom which the teacher expected would help students in improving their. Usually, teacher gave students two presentation practices as a way to check students' performance. To improve students', the class teacher recorded the practices with a video camera, which recording would be uploaded to class blog. The teacher used the videos as a way of giving feedbacks to his students about the strength and weaknesses of their presentation. Using the feedback and the video, students were expected to be able to improve their presentation performance for Oral Test. Beyond essay and presentation consultation, the teacher also used soc-meds to motivate his students in their study.

Final Result

At the first experiment of using FB Group and classblog, the result was satisfyingly good. From 18 students in this class, 17 passed the final test and one failed because of not taking OT. For Written Test, the average correct answers of MC section was 35 and the average final score was 3.3.

Table 1. Score of High Intermediate 4: Term 1/2012

Students	Daily Performance	Written Test				Oral Test	Final Score
		W	S	Raw	Con		
A	3.5	25	23	48	1.75	3.8	3.1
B	3.7	26	36	62	2.75	3.6	3.3
C	3.8	23	32	55	2.25	3.6	3.2
D	3.5	24	29	53	2.0	3.6	3.1
E	3.7	21	3.6	57	2.5	3.7	3.3
F	3.6	25	40	65	3.0	0	0
G	3.6	24	38	62	2.75	3.7	3.4
H	3.6	22	29	51	2.0	3.7	3.2
I	3.7	25	38	63	3.0	3.6	3.5
J	3.7	25	30	55	2.25	3.7	3.3
K	3.6	25	38	63	3	3.7	3.5
L	3.6	24	32	56	2.25	3.6	3.2
M	3.6	25	35	60	2.75	3.5	3.3
N	3.6	29	51	80	4.5	3.8	4
O	3.7	24	37	61	2.75	3.7	3.4
P	3.7	26	39	65	3	3.7	3.5
Q	3.6	20	34	54	2.25	3.6	3.2
Average	3.6	24.3	35.11	59	2.63	3.66	3.34

To find out the effect of class blog and FB group from students' perspective, the teacher distributed questionnaires to his students to get feedbacks about using class blog and FB group for two terms in a row. The questionnaires were distributed via FB Message to students but only 10 questionnaires were returned. Students' feedbacks were positive in which students found the blog and FB group beneficial in helping them during regular study period and preparing them for final exam. They thought the PDFs of TOEFL test and its listening material improved their test-taking skills, especially the listening part. The slideshows of grammar material also gave students a chance to repeat the lesson several times until they understood it. Furthermore, the online quizzes were a great support for students who needed extra exercises. The results are as follows.

Apakah grup kelas di FB membantu kegiatan belajar selama di HI-4?

Seperti apakah manfaat grup Facebook bagi Anda? (boleh pilih lebih dari satu jawaban) ?

Seringkah Anda memberi respons di grup Facebook?

Apakah blog kelas membantu Anda belajar di HI 3?

Seperti apakah manfaat blog kelas bagi Anda? (boleh pilih lebih dari satu jawaban)

Seringkah Anda memberi respons di blog kelas?

Apabila Anda menuliskan pos di blog/grup Facebook, seringkah guru kelas membalas?

Apa yang biasanya Anda poskan di blog/grup Facebook?

10. Dari pengalaman selama ini, masukan apa yang bisa diberikan untuk meningkatkan blog kelas dan grup Facebook di masa mendatang?
- Informasi tentang jadwal tambahan lebih jelas lagi, terutama jika ada perpindahan kelas.
 - Tidak ada keluhan.
 - Tidak ada. Share materi lewat FB dan Posterous jadi berguna sekali.
 - Saran saya agar di kelas di bentuk grup untuk membahas English grammar yang menurut sangat penting untuk *writing*.

Despite all the benefits, students' participation in FB group and class blog was low. In FB group, the teacher was the most dominant person who posted content while students were silent readers, reading all teacher's posts in FB and class blog and rarely asked questions regarding lesson materials. In classblog, the online quiz was done by less than ten students and the number of participation decreased from time to time. The only thing that students did in FB group was liking teacher's post or posting their essay drafts. If they asked questions, they were only about class schedule, permission to be absent, and asking about final test or presentation preparation. Based on the questionnaires, the main problem of students' low participation in FB group and blog was caused by limited access to internet. There were two students who did not have internet access at home while those who did had limited access to internet. According to students, their internet access at home were time-based while some others had problems with slow connection. Opening FB account was quite easy but accessing class blog requires more time, especially when they wanted to download audio or video files. So if they spent too much time to download videos or audios, they would have to spend much money from their phone credits (in case of mobile internet) or charge much on house telephone bills. Nevertheless, they thought that FB group and class blog were a fantastic tool of assisting them in their study and test preparation. As on teacher's side, the soc-meds were really the ideal tools to reach his students wherever they were and engage them in their learning process.

Evaluation

As predicted, the great incentive of soc-med in HI 3 and 4 level was to allow teacher to engage students in their learning process in and outside classroom. With FB or email, teacher could extend his teaching and students could submit their essay draft three or four times a week. On Monday and Wednesday, students discussed their essay drafts with their teacher in classroom and they discuss it again on Saturday or Sunday.

Even though the teacher had applied essay consultation via internet, some students in class still took for granted the importance of writing their essays regularly. The teacher again had to deal with students who progressed slowly in revising and developing their essay drafts, which were worrying if they could have not done it before Final test on March. To counter this matter, the teacher simply posted progress report of students essay drafts using FB Note. By posting the report on FB group, every student in class had knowledge about his/her progress in comparison to his/her other classmates. In turn, the note created a psychological pressure that pushed slow students to write their drafts more diligently and finished it on time.

The Second Experiment

Despite all of the problems in the first experiment, the class teacher was satisfied with the result and confident to continue this approach in his next HI-3 class, Term 2/2012. Again, there were 17 students all together and they would stay together in HI-4. Just like previous class, the teacher began the class by telling them that they had to join class group in FB and class blog. Most students had Facebook accounts and the teacher immediately added them to class FB group. Those who did not have accounts were persuaded to open accounts. As to class blog, the teacher invited students to join class blog via email.

Drawing lessons from the past, the teacher abandoned online quiz in class blog because he thought his students would not do online quizzes for similar reasons as his previous students. Instead, the teacher chose to concentrate on sharing lesson materials in the form of PDFs and videocasts via blogs. For example, in HI-3, the teacher created videocasts for all lessons in student book and shared them on Posterous. The aim of videocasts was to help students to review lessons at home, in case they did not understand teacher's explanation in class or missed a class session. Besides that, the videocasts included lesson materials and grammar points in each lesson. Additionally, the students also got extra exercise (in Word) on grammar points, which they could download and worked on outside class. Later, students would discuss the answer of grammar exercise in the next meeting or through FB. Unlike the first experiment, class teacher intensified FB as a way of getting in touch with students by, for example, greeting them, talking about recent issues, share links to interesting things in internet.

In term 3/2012, the class teacher continued internet approach with the same students. For efficiency matter, the class teacher did not create any videocast for the lessons in HI-4's student book as HI-4, students and class teacher would be busy with essay writing and preparing slideshows for final test. So, rather than filling class blog with videocasts, the teacher uploaded TOEFL test material to prepare students for the final test of HI-4, Written part especially. The TOEFL test materials; Reading, Structure & Listening; were taken from a TOEFL preparation book that was scanned into PDF and uploaded into class blog. The idea of giving TOEFL preparation test came from the class teacher's experience with his past HI-4 classes who scored less than 30 correct items in Written test. The part where students made the most mistakes were Listening section. To his understanding and his students' feedbacks, they had problem with Listening part simply because they were not familiar with listening to non-scripted audio material. Therefore, the class teacher tackled the problem by uploading audio files that accompany the listening section of TOEFL test to class blog. Through FB group and in classroom, the class teacher encouraged his students to check class blog and download the TOEFL preparation test material for their home exercise. By downloading PDFs, students had the freedom of doing the exercise offline and, with audio files, they were able to practice and hone their listening skill. Another function of classblog is to showcase the videos of students' presentation practice which was expected to give feedback to students performance.

Final Result

The end result of the second experiment showed that FB group and class blog were successful in increasing HI 4 students' performance. In terms of Final Test, the scores are significantly higher than the first experiment class. For example, the average correct answers in MC part was 39, while the first experiment class got 35 correct answers. The high score in MC part was made possible by the fact that 10 students in the second class got 40 correct items, whereas only 2 students of the previous class who got >40 correct items. The Conversion score of the second experiment class was 2.69, a slight increased of 2.63 in the first experiment class. All in all, the average final score of HI-4 students increased a little to 3.35. It should be noted that the average final score of the first experiment class was 3.34 because there was a student who did not do OT which in turn affected the average score of the whole class.

Table 2. Score of High Intermediate 4: Term 3/2012

Students	Daily Performance	Written Test				Oral Test	Final Score
		W	S	Raw	Con		
A	3.6	26	41	67	3	3.1	3.2
B	3.5	21	34	55	2	3.7	3.1
C	3.9	23	37	60	2.5	3.5	3.2
D	3.4	17	22	30	10	30	2.5
E	3.5	21	37	58	2.25	3.8	3.2
F	3.7	25	41	66	3	4.1	3.7
G	3.6	20	44	64	2.75	3.7	3.4
H	3.6	22	37	59	2.5	3.4	3.2
I	3.7	21	29	50	1.75	3.5	3
J	3.7	22	47	69	3.25	4	3.7
K	3.6	22	35	57	2.25	4.1	3.4
L	3.6	23	40	63	2.75	3.8	3.4
M	3.6	25	47	72	3.5	4	3.7
N	3.6	25	43	68	3.25	3.4	3.4
O	3.7	27	41	68	3.25	3.7	3.6
P	3.7	26	44	30	3.25	3,8	3.6
Q	3.7	25	48	73	3.5	4	3.8
Average	3.63	23	39	59.3	2.69	3.68	3.35

For essay writing in classroom, students made great progress in finishing their papers two weeks before Final Test, since students did essay consultation 3 or 4 times a week. The consultation via FB group also speeded up students PowerPoint consultation. Another benefit of FB group and classblog is the videos of students' presentation practice, shared via classblog, also assisted them in improving their presentation performance. The questionnaires given to students after class also support the result where most students expressed their agreement on how FB group and class blog facilitated them in HI-3 and 4 study

Questionnaire Result of HI 4/Term 3 (2012)

Seringkah Anda memberi respons di grup Facebook?

Apakah blog kelas membantu kegiatan belajar selama di HI-4?

Seperti apakah manfaat blog kelas bagi Anda? (boleh pilih lebih dari satu jawaban)

Seringkah Anda memberi respons di blog kelas?

Apabila Anda menuliskan pos di blog/grup Facebook, seringkah guru kelas membalas?

Apa Videocast di blog membantu Anda dalam belajar?

9. Apa yang biasanya Anda poskan di blog/grup Facebook?

Conclusion

After 12 intensive months, the research concludes that blog and Facebook are amazingly useful to support teaching and learning activities outside classroom. Internet made it possible for a teacher to interact with his students beyond the boundaries of time and space. More than that, the internet enabled the teacher to add extra materials--audios, videos, office docs--which students can use for their study at home, hence increasing their comprehension of the lessons they got in the classroom and creating an continual learning condition. Another incentive of using internet, sharing extra lesson materials on class blog reduce students' expenses because they can view the materials on their computer. If they need hard copy, they just print it themselves. Additionally, Facebook allows teacher and students to communicate on academic matter without putting much expense on both of the teacher and students' sides.

However, blending socmed and socnet with classroom activities may pose problems that students and class teacher have to deal with from the beginning. The possible problems are limited access to internet, students reluctance to participate, providing content materials, and

internet/computer fluency for students and class teacher. Although the teacher may have internet access, she/he cannot be sure that all of her/his students have the same accessibility. So, the teacher must prepare a solution, if a few students in the classroom cannot take part in classblog and socnet. Even if students have internet facilities, some of them might not be willing to participate in classblog or soc-net for personal reason. The next problem is that the class teacher must be resourceful in creating lesson contents that she/he wants to put in the blog/soc-net. She/he cannot rely on materials on internet all the time, since the materials may not be suitable to support the lessons in students textbook. The teacher should either find materials which really match students' book or create tailor-made materials. To do the later, the teacher must be very fluent in finding and using computer softwares that suit the task of creating and developing lesson materials, such as, turning Word docs into PDF files, making audio/videopodcasts, editing audio/vide files, using features of blogs. If teacher can master all the skills needed, she/he should be able to guide her/his students to use the classblog and socnet which have been prepared.

Based on the problems presented above, integrating soc-net and soc-med in classroom will work properly only if the following requirements are met. For a start, the teacher and students alike are ready and familiar with these internet tools; blog and socnet. Teacher should have decent internet connection and she/he should be ready with solutions for students who have limited internet access. It will be great there is enough internet facility inside classroom. Lastly, the class teacher has to be able to learn computer softwares and exploit them in creating content materials for blog and socnet.

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